

Cadomian ophiolites in the Ossa-Morena Complex: where and why

Ricardo Arenas^{1*}, Rubén Díez Fernández², Esther Rojo-Pérez¹, Irene Novo-Fernández¹, José Manuel Fuenlabrada³, Richard Albert⁴, Sonia Sánchez Martínez¹, Pilar Andonaegui¹ & Antonio García-Casco⁵

¹*Departamento de Mineralogía y Petrología and Instituto de Geociencias (UCM, CSIC), Universidad Complutense. Madrid, Spain*

²*Instituto Geológico y Minero de España – CSIC. Salamanca, Spain*

³*Unidad de Geocronología (CAI de Ciencias de la Tierra y Arqueometría), Universidad Complutense. Madrid, Spain*

⁴*Institut für Geowissenschaften, Goethe-University Frankfurt. Frankfurt am Main, Germany*

⁵*Departamento de Mineralogía y Petrología and Instituto Andaluz de Ciencias de la Tierra (UGR, CSIC), Universidad de Granada. Granada, Spain*

*arenas@ucm.es

The Ossa-Morena Complex contains a stack of units with different origin and tectonothermal evolution (Fig. 1; Díez Fernández & Arenas 2015, Arenas et al. 2016). This structure hampers its previous interpretation as a geotectonic zone of the Iberian Massif representative of a common section of the Gondwana margin. Different units of the complex record a previous Cadomian history, which is considered a characteristic of the SW Iberian Massif. Cadomian evolution has traditionally been interpreted in relation to the dynamics of a peri-Gondwanan volcanic arc, the remains of which can be identified in the units located below the Torreárboles Fm. (lowest Cambrian). Recent work in these units has allowed identification of different terranes whose origin is discussed based on new data. The correct interpretation of these terranes is a key issue to approach the reconstruction of the Ediacaran margin of Gondwana in NW Africa. In particular, two Ediacaran ophiolitic units have been recognized, with different characteristics from those of the volcanic arc itself: the Calzadilla Ophiolite (Arenas et al. 2018) and the Mérida Ophiolite (Díez Fernández et al. 2021). The Calzadilla Ophiolite is found in the central section of Ossa-Morena (Fig. 1) and is formed by ultramafic and subordinate mafic rocks with compositional characteristics of boninites generated in a supra-subduction zone (SSZ) context and dated at c. 600 Ma (Arenas et al. 2018). The ophiolite shows tectonic contacts with roughly synchronous siliciclastic materials belonging to the Serie Negra (Black Series), and is affected by a main event of Cadomian deformation and metamorphism dated at c. 540 Ma (Arenas et al. 2018). Based on these characteristics, the Calzadilla Ophiolite has been interpreted as representative of a fore-arc basin. Further north, in the Obejo Valsequillo Domain, the Mérida Ophiolite appears stacked between two units of continental or arc affinity (Fig. 1). Their mafic lithologies have calc-alkaline and tholeiitic affinities, that indicate generation in a SSZ-type context and have been dated at c. 577 Ma (Bandrés et al. 2004). The ophiolite shows Cadomian metamorphism (c. 555 Ma; Bandrés et al. 2004) with prograde P-T path and peak conditions at c. 700°C and 8 kbar. The Mérida Ophiolite likely generated in a back-arc basin, opened between the volcanic arc and the outer margin of Gondwana. As additional data to consider the two Ediacaran ophiolites as different lithospheric sections from the magmatic arc itself, it should be noted that they present a completely different Nd isotopic composition, which prevents their development from the same mantle wedge.

The origin of the Ediacaran terranes of the Ossa-Morena Complex, their structural and metamorphic evolutions and their distribution in the orogen, allow to propose an evolutionary model for the Gondwana margin during this period (Arenas et al. 2018, Díez Fernández et al. 2021). The model includes the initial activity of a peri-Gondwanan volcanic arc and the successive opening of a fore-arc basin (c. 600 Ma) and a back-arc basin (c. 577 Ma), followed by a progressive collision episode of the continental margin with the arc. The collision favored the closure of the back-arc basin, the accretion of the Merida Ophiolite under the arc (c. 555 Ma) and its final obduction above the Gondwana margin. These tectonic processes

were followed by the closure of the fore-arc basin and the obduction of the Calzadilla Ophiolite onto the arc itself (c. 540 Ma). The Cadomian evolution of this peri-Gondwanan section continued with the collapse of the colliding ensemble and its erosive leveling, followed by the generation of a new episode of intense magmatic activity in the arc and the unconformable deposition of the Malcocinado Fm., constituted by calc-alkaline igneous rocks and located directly under the Torreárboles Fm.

Figure 1. Zonation of the Iberian Massif and location of the Calzadilla and Mérida ophiolites (CO and MO, respectively). AF, Azuaga Fault; BAO, Beja-Acebuches Ophiolite; CA, Carvalho Amphibolites; CF, Canaleja Fault; CMU, Cubito-Moura Unit; BCU, Badajoz-Córdoba Unit; ET, Espina Thrust; HF, Hornachos Fault; IOMZO, Internal Ossa-Morena Complex Ophiolites; LLF, Llanos Fault; MLF, Malpica-Lamego Fault; OF, Onza Fault; OVD, Obejo-Valsequillo Domain; PG-CVD, Puente Génave-Castelo de Vide Detachment; PRF, Palas de Rei Fault; PTF, Porto-Tomar Fault; RF, Riás Fault; VF, Viveiro Fault. After Díez Fernández & Arenas (2015) and Arenas et al. (2016).

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